

Ernesto AZZURRO, CERRI J. TESTAGROSSA A., LEK team

Institute for Environmental Protection and Research (ISPRA), Italy and Zoological Station A. Dohrn, Villa comunale, Napoli, Italy / Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn (SZN), Villa Comunale 80121 Napoli, Italy

E-mail: eazzurr@gmail.com

ADVANCES IN MONITORING SPATIO-TEMPORAL TRENDS FOR MEDITERRANEAN BIOINVASION RESEARCH AND MARINE PROTECTED AREAS

Abstract

Determining the distribution of invasive species and tracing back their spatio-temporal dynamics, is crucial to feed early warning systems, risk assessments and to mitigate impacts through management actions. However, in the marine environment, this task can be particularly problematic because historical data are often missing and biological invasions can be neglected until they become sufficiently abundant and pose socio-economical concerns.

Here, drawing on recent experiences on Local Ecological Knowledge (LEK) and on its application through different Mediterranean countries, we report three different case studies to exemplify potential applications of eliciting LEK to retrace the dynamics of marine invaders. A growing interest on these methodologies is highlighted in either Mediterranean studies and worldwide, reflecting the need of broad ecological observations and by the LEK value as a mutually beneficial action to social and ecological systems. The application of standard LEK protocols across boundaries and jurisdictions can overcome some of the limits of bio-invasion research, providing a strategic and practical complement to traditional surveys and occasional species records. This practice is now being transferred to Mediterranean Marine Protected Areas and tested for the monitoring and management needs of small-scale fishery.

Key-words: Non-indigenous species, poleward range expansions, mapping, management.

Introduction

Tracing out the spatio-temporal dynamics of non-indigenous species is crucial for risk assessments, early warning systems and to unravel ecological factors underlying the emergence and spread of biological invasions. However, surveying marine environments is more challenging than for terrestrial ecosystems and researchers are seldom capable to monitor species distribution in real time or to fully understand historical changes, especially over large geographical scales. These difficulties ultimately lead to incomplete or missing information in existing datasets which might prevent us from reconstructing invasion dynamics back to their emergence. In the last two decades, as a partial solution to unsatisfactory ecological information, researchers, policy makers and Marine Protected Areas, became interested into the available ecological information that could be obtained from local communities living in close contact with nature. This knowledge, often termed “*Local Ecological Knowledge*” (LEK), can be defined as the ‘information that a group of people has about local ecosystems’. We must consider that social groups such fishermen and divers rely on the marine ecosystem for their livelihood and gain ecological information through their everyday experience. Accessing this knowledge provides new opportunities for marine research, while achieving broader goals such as increased awareness and environmental literacy. In this paper, we will consider a few case studies

to illustrate potential applications of LEK to study and monitoring biological invasions in the Mediterranean realm.

Materials and methods

LEK data are generated through a collective and coordinated effort based on the volunteer engagement of an international team of researchers and technicians (LEK team) well connected with local fishery communities. Small scale-fishermen were interviewed face-to-face, through a standard semi-structured interview protocol, developed and implemented by a number of Mediterranean research programs (see acknowledgements). Respondents were asked to reconstruct changes in both distribution and abundances of marine species, retrospectively. Fishermen ranked each species on a yearly timeline and through 6 classes of abundance: “Absent”, “Rare (observed once per year)”, “Occasional (observed sometimes in a fishing period)”, “Common (regularly observed in a fishing period)”, “Abundant” (regularly observed and abundant in a fishing period), “Dominant” (observed at every fishing session and with great abundances in a fishing period). Respondents draw a line on a pre-printed diagramming table, to express how these abundances had changed across time (see Annex 1). This graphical approach was adopted to facilitate memory retrieval, minimizing cognitive effort and recall bias. Moreover, interviews were supported by illustrated identification manuals, to help fishermen assigning each species correctly and to check for consistency and knowledge in respondents’ judgements. Examples provided here are extracted from a much larger dataset (Azzurro et al. *in prep*), which includes interviews realized in 95 locations, across 9 countries and 7 different subsectors in the Mediterranean. In the participating countries, specific trainings on the application of the interview protocol were provided through both, theoretical lessons and demonstrations of practical interviews made in collaboration with local fishermen. Participating researchers were guided in performing standardized interviews and advised on how to limit risks of potential biases, such as the ones related to taxonomical identification and ‘memory recall’ bias (Hassan, 2006). Data gathered from this collaborative effort was used to gain information on both indigenous and non-indigenous species, perceived as ‘new’ or increasing in each fishing area. In our first case (*Case I*), we extracted spatio-temporal data in perceived abundances of the indigenous range-expanding bluefish *Pomatomus saltatrix* from the Ligurian Sea and used breakpoint analysis to establish in which year respondents noted this species to have increased the most in abundance. Breakpoints, corresponding to years when the time series of perceived abundances differed from the overall trend, were assessed through changepoint detection based on the residual sum of squares (Zelleis et al., 2015). We also explored how first records were associated with the longitude of the various fishing areas from which respondents came from. In our second case (*Case II*), we extracted the first sighting of the bluespotted cornetfish (*Fistularia commersonii*) (N = 154 interviewed people) filtering out those reported before the onset of the invasion in 2000 (N = 28). These georeferenced points were sorted along the temporal and latitudinal axes and compared with the known chronology of the species. In the third example (*Case III*) we show how to map the perceived abundances of an invader. We took the case of the Atlantic Blue crab (*Callinectes sapidus*), in the Lesina lagoon, a saltwater marsh located on the Adriatic coast, in Southern Italy. The interview protocol was here implemented with a section in which respondents were asked to draw how the perceived abundances varied in space. For this latter task, a participatory mapping methodology (Fagerholm et al., 2012) was used and 25 fishermen participated to draw sectors with homogeneous

abundances on a pre-printed map. Then abundances were imported by researchers on a vectorial grid on QGIS. Cohen's kappa was adopted to verify the agreement between respondents on how the Atlantic blue crab varied its abundances in the lagoon.

Results and discussion

Case I: The bluefish *Pomatomus saltatrix* is not an exotic species for the Mediterranean Sea, but its outbreak in the Ligurian sea is a good example to demonstrate how the arrival and subsequent increase in abundance of a species can be traced back to its emergence. Indeed, most of the interviewed fishermen had never seen this fish before the nineties. Fig. 1 shows a rapid increase in (perceived) densities, with significant breakpoints identified in three distinct occasions: 1996, 2003 and 2009. This means that in about 20 years, the bluefish jumped from the lowest levels of abundance (rare or absent) to the level of a common species, which much interacts with fishing activities and other native predators, such as *Dicentrarchus labrax*. This information is now used to feed vulnerability assessments and to support management plans of local Marine Protected Areas (*i.e.* Portofino MPA).

Fig.1: The bluefish *Pomatomus saltatrix* is indigenous for the Mediterranean, but the temporal evolution of perceived abundances show as this species was formerly very rare in the Ligurian Sea (NW Mediterranean). Breakpoint analysis highlights three breakpoint years in 1996, 2003 and 2006. DATA extracted from the LEK team database: Query: *Pomatomus saltatrix*/Ligurian Sea; N = 52 interviewed fishermen.

Case II: LEK generated data are also coherent with the spatio-temporal dynamics of the invasion. By extracting the first LEK generated sightings of *F. commersonii* in the Mediterranean Sea, we can appreciate as the temporal evolution of this species reconstructed through fishermen's observations followed an East to West gradient,

matching both, the direction and the spread rates reported by the scientific literature (Azzurro *et al.*, 2011). This exercise illustrates how the history of a marine bio-invasion can be reconstructed at the regional scale and through a coordinated observation system (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Relationship between the latitude and the year of the first sightings of the bluest spotted cornetfish as reported by fishermen’s interviews (N = 126)

Case III: In our third case we show LEK as a valuable tool for mapping the distribution of invasive species. Our experience with the fishermen of the Lesina Lagoon (Azzurro *et al.*, *in prep*) proved that respondents had a relatively good level of agreement about the spatial distribution of the Atlantic blue crab *C. sapidus* (Cohen’s kappa = 0.38; Fig. 3). Moreover, changepoint analysis demonstrates that this species increased its densities after 2010, becoming a dominant invader in the saltmarsh community after 2005. Looking at the participatory map (Fig. 3), it is clear that the invader is widely distributed in the lagoon, reaching its highest abundances in the North-Eastern sectors. The high level of agreement between respondents demonstrates the potential of LEK for mapping the abundance and distribution of invasive species and this low-cost approach could be particularly relevant whenever information from ecological surveys is scarce or not available (like in our case study). Moreover, LEK-based participatory mapping (see also Chambers *et al.*, 2006) might be extremely useful for monitoring species abundances during the application of control measures. In this context, rapid assessments made in collaboration with local communities can be very informative to understand how biological invaders respond to such initiatives, either in terms of their abundances and in their spatial distribution. A similar application of LEK for participatory mapping could also be extended to those contexts where a non-indigenous species are subjected to intensive commercial exploitation. These are just some examples to show the potential of monitoring marine bioinvasions by accessing LEK in a standard, structured and coordinated manner. A complementary monitoring approach, which empowers the

observational potential and awareness of people living in intimate relationship with the natural environment.

Fig. 3: Distribution of the Atlantic blue crab (*Callinectes sapidus*) in the Lesina lagoon, Italy as reconstructed by a participatory mapping exercise realized with (N = 25) small-scale fishermen during the period March-June 2008. Values ranged from “Rare” (light yellow) to “Dominant” (dark red). Cohen’s kappa = 0.38. The upper graph shows the breakpoint analysis of the temporal evolution of average abundances of this species in the same area.

Conclusions

We are all living through an age when there is a sense and a reality of accelerating change, with dramatical ecological alterations often happening before our eyes. Hopefully our case studies can help to explain how the everyday experience of people living in close contact with these changes can be used to provide relevant information to contemporary ecologists and decision makers (see also Raymond *et al.*, 2010). In relation to the issue of Mediterranean bio-invasions, specific social groups such as small-scale fishermen and divers can be particularly informative and LEK actions can be effective in empowering them in detecting, monitoring, mapping and ultimately managing these species. If properly elicited, LEK can be adopted to integrate (or to replace if absent any other source of data), available ecological information from environmental surveys. Moreover, the use of semi-structured protocols for the elicitation of LEK could disclose further applications to understand how relevant stakeholders perceive biological invasions in relation to their ecological, cultural and economic dimension. We argue that a wide adoption of LEK might help researchers and policymakers both to better understand and to have more updated pictures about invasion dynamics at the local or even regional level. These processes need to be systematic and coordinated across boundaries and jurisdictions to ensure common responses to a common environmental problem.

Ethical statement

Data collection was confidential, as interviewers did not record any sensitive personal information about respondents. At the beginning of the interview, respondents were informed about the purposes of the study and gave informed consent to use the provided information for scientific purposes.

Acknowledgements

The Mediterranean LEK initiative was initially conceived by the international basin-wide monitoring program *CIESM Tropical Signals*; and a standard protocols (LEK-1) was adopted by the projects *Interreg BALMAS*; *FAO-AdriaMed* and *FAO-MedSudMed*; and recently supported by the Interreg Med Programme (Grant number Pr MPA-Adapt 1MED15_3.2_M2_337) 85% co-funded by the European Regional Development Fund, which implemented the use of LEK protocols (LEK-1 and LEK-2) for Marine Protected Areas, transferring the methodology to the Public Institutions of: Brijuni National Park (Croatia), MPA Pelagie Islands (Italy), Consortium of Management of Portofino MPA (Italy), National Park of Port-Cros (France), and the Corsican Agency for Environment (France). We kindly acknowledge for his valuable help on data management Valerio Sbragaglia, ISPRA, Livorno, Italy. This work was made possible through the contribution of all Mediterranean fishermen, which shared with us their observations. We warmly thank them as well as all the esteemed researchers and MPA technicians and managers which adopted the LEK protocol, contributing to foster the use of this methodology at the Mediterranean level. **The LEK team:** Michel Bariche - American University of Beirut, Beirut, Lebanon; Giulio Busoni, University of Pisa, Italy; Antoniadou Chryssanthi - Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece; Jamila Ben Souissi - INAT Tunis, Tunisia; Martina Hervat - National Park of Brijuni, Croatia; Akram Al-Turky - Marine Biology Research Center, Libya; Lovrence Lipej - National Institute of Biology, Piran, Slovenia; Luca Ceriola - FAO/MedSudMed, Rome, Italy; Nicoletta Milone - FAO/AdriaMed, Rome, Italy; Federica Pannacciulli - ENEA S. Teresa, Italy; Giovanni Vargiu - Ente Parco Asinara, Italy; Guglielmo Letterio - University of Messina, Italy; Carlotta Mazzoldi - University of Padova, Padova, Italy; Fabio Grati and Luca Bolognini - ISMAR Ancona, Italy; Paula Moschella - CIESM, Monaco, France; Nur Eda Topçu - Istanbul University, Istanbul, Turkey; Fabrizio Gianni - Université Côte d'Azur, CNRS, France; Yanna Samuel-Rhoads, University of Cyprus, Cyprus; Joanna Tomanic, and A. Joksimovic, Z., University of Montenegro, Kotor, Montenegro; Jerina Kolutari - Agricultural University Durres, Albania; Luca Saponari - University of Milano Bicocca, Italy.

Bibliography

- AZZURRO E., SOTO S., GAROFALO G., MAYNOU F. (2013) - *Fistularia commersonii* in the Mediterranean Sea: invasion history and distribution modeling based on presence-only records. *Biological Invasions*, 15(5): 977-990.
- CHAMBERS R. (2006) - Participatory mapping and geographic information systems: whose map? Who is empowered and who disempowered? Who gains and who loses?. *The Electronic Journal of Information Systems in Developing Countries*, 25(1): 1- 11
- FAGERHOLM N., KÄYHKÖ N., NDUMBARO F., KHAMIS M. (2012) - Community stakeholders' knowledge in landscape assessments—Mapping indicators for landscape services. *Ecological Indicators*, 18: 421-433.
- HASSAN E. (2006) - Recall bias can be a threat to retrospective and prospective research designs. *The Internet Journal of Epidemiology*, 3(2): 339-412.
- RAYMOND C.M, FAZEY I., REED M.S., STRINGER L.C., ROBINSON G.M., EVELY A.C. (2010) - Integrating local and scientific knowledge for environmental management. *Journal of environmental management*, 91(8): 1766-1777.
- ZEILEIS A., LEISCH F., HORNIK K., KLEIBER C., HANSEN B., MERKLE E.C., ZEILEIS M.A. (2015) - *Package 'strucchange'*. Technical Report, 69 pp.